

Sustainable Digital Transformation and Space Exploration – A Literature Review

^[1] Shaikh Farisa ^[2] Aditi Jadhav ^[3] Deepika Dubey
^{[1][2][3]} Assistant Professor in UDICT MGMU

Abstract

Digital transformation necessitates connection that allows for "anything", "anytime", and "anywhere". Space, as a driver of digital change, has emerged as a focal point for socioeconomic sustainability and progress. Disruptive occurrences are those that have historically changed our planet. COVID-19 has driven governments and businesses to pursue reform, particularly in the digital space. Space has enabled a number of sectoral programs, including agricultural, defense, and marine. Mega constellations provide telecom services over the world and will compete directly with terrestrial telecom carriers in the next years, while telecom operators should focus on investing in 5G infrastructure. The most potential mega constellation is Starlink's, which will include approximately 40,000 satellites in Low Earth Orbit (LEO) and provide service coverage throughout the entire Earth's surface. It should be noted that there is no European initiative of this size. The Starlink mega constellation's strength is its total vertical integration, with a single set of enterprises designing, producing, launching, controlling, operating, and providing telecom services. The economies of scale that would be obtained might reduce retail pricing of telecom services to levels that terrestrial telecom carriers would find unprofitable. This paper will present an outline of how Europe and its member states have been planning for space-related activities in conjunction with non-space activities to support the country's digital transformation. The purpose of this study is to give insights into the current stage of digital transformation and to identify possibilities for further research.

Introduction

The COVID-19 pandemic has highlighted the importance of digital skills in the economy and society, prompting governments and companies to focus on digital transformation. Key indicators for sustainable businesses include connectivity, digital skills, advanced technologies like big data, and digital public services like telemedicine. The International Telecommunications Union (ITU) estimates that an increase in mobile broadband penetration can lead to a 1.5% increase in GDP. The digital transformation requires connectivity providing "anything, anytime, and anywhere." Space is crucial for socioeconomic sustainability and growth, and mega constellations will directly compete with terrestrial telecom operators in the coming years. Telecom operators should focus on investing in 5G infrastructure and enhancing their digital skills to ensure a more sustainable future.

Starlink, a European company, is planning a mega constellation of over 4000 satellites in Low Earth Orbit (LEO) covering the entire Earth's surface. The Starlink mega constellation is unique in its complete vertical integration, including satellite design, manufacturing, launching, control, operation, and telecom service provision by a single group of companies. This could lower retail prices for telecom services, making European terrestrial operators less viable. However, Starlink's success may lead to a strong dependency on the non-European Starlink mega constellation, highlighting the potential for significant economic benefits for European telecommunications.

Table 1.0 Understanding challenges with European Union (EU)

Telecom operators' cash flow problems	While European telecommunications providers have paid for the spectrum needed for 5G and are investing considerably in infrastructure for the roll out of 5G services, they are projected to lose customers as a result of the availability of Starlink services.
Satellite telecom manufacturing industry loss of competitiveness	The European sector will be excluded from the mega constellations' production chain, resulting in a knowledge and expertise gap. Furthermore, the sales of other types of telecom satellites (i.e. GEO) in the European sector will be greatly reduced due to the predicted fall in demand as a result of the availability of Starlink services.
Terrestrial telecom manufacturing industry decrease of sales	The terrestrial (fixed plus wireless) telecom network incorporates a wide range of gear (base stations, DSLAMs, switches, antennas, fiber, and so on) and software developed by European firms. Retail telecom services will be provided directly to end users via the mega constellation's satellites, rendering terrestrial infrastructure unnecessary.
Loss of European independence in telecommunications	The reliance on a non-EU operator to provide telecom services, as well as the decline of the European terrestrial & satellite manufacturing industries, will be significant barriers to the development and operation of European telecommunications networks and services. Subsequent issues would arise in the supply of European government (terrestrial and satellite) communications services.

Europe might respond by building, producing, and deploying a mega constellation of equal size and/or capabilities aimed at first governmental satellite communications (GOVSATCOM) and then providing wholesale telecom services to terrestrial telecom operators in the 5G era. The European mega constellation might complement rather than compete with the terrestrial infrastructure of European operators, which will require increased capacity, content delivery, security, and high availability for the impending 5G networks. Furthermore, by combining this networking strategy with the EuroQCI's innovative quantum technologies, the European sector

will gain a competitive advantage [6,7]. The deployment of the European mega constellation might be phased to fit market demand and make the most use of financing resources. This is conceivable owing to the unique economic model compared to the Starlink giant constellation. Instead of deploying the entire mega constellation in one step to cover all potential retail users, the European approach will utilize the advantage of complementarily with terrestrial networks and will expand in response to commercial users' capacity demand.

Literature Survey

The European Union has been doing a variety of preparatory initiatives to facilitate the EU and its Member States' digital transition in a safe, resilient, and sustainable manner [8]. In the message "Shaping Europe's digital future" published in February 2020, the European Commission outlined its vision for digital transformation, aiming to achieve a welcoming use of tech that works for people while respecting EU basic values. Digital technologies are regarded as a critical component in this change, while all stakeholders are becoming more aware of the importance of an industry 4.0 strategy and enhanced stakeholder engagement. However, coordination among member states' ministries and stakeholders is still lacking.

The Commission's new digital strategy is built around two pillars: the White Paper on Artificial Intelligence and the European Data Strategy. On March 10, 2020, the Commission unveiled its new SME strategy for a sustainable and digital Europe. On April 28, 2021, the EU rule creating the Union Space Programme and the European Union Space Agency was released. The rule provides the legal foundation for establishing a GOVSATCOM system. GOVSATCOM is a civil and governmental satellite communications service that provides satellite communications capacity and services to Union and Member State authorities in charge of security-critical missions and infrastructures.

According to the regulation, the GOVSATCOM use-cases should be able to be analyzed by the relevant actors for three main families: crisis management, which could encompass civilian and military Common Security and Defence missions and activities, natural and man-made

disasters, humanitarian situations, and maritime emergencies; surveillance, which may include surround surveillance, pre-frontier surveillance, sea-border monitoring, maritime surveillance, and surveillance of illegal activities.

The European Union is now preparing its next space flagship initiative in the realm of connectivity, as announced by Commissioner Breton on July 15. The Commissioner remarked, "We already need to look beyond 5G." I'm talking about starting to prepare for 6G, but not just that. The next paradigm change is about combining connection and space to enable high-speed connectivity throughout Europe."

The European Union intends to invest in the construction of a new integrated, secure, and autonomous space communication system that will complement the EU's world-class satellite navigation and Earth observation systems, Galileo and Copernicus [9,10,11]. The European Commission intends to expand this cornerstone of the "European Secure Connectivity Initiative" by combining existing programs and activities of the Commission, the European Space Agency, and Member States, as well as developing new ones. It is envisaged that space and terrestrial infrastructures be integrated in order to offer.

The Govsatcom component of the European Union's Space Programme (which will offer the first core of available services by pooling and sharing existing satellite capacity) and an additional space segment (based on a multi-orbit network) will be created to supplement these basic capabilities. The new space section will provide increased communication capabilities and will use the revolutionary quantum technology developed by the EuroQCI effort.⁴ A number of ESA efforts related to this program are also underway within the ARTES Programme, including Scylight/Hydrion/SAGA, 4S, and 5G. The flagship is projected to improve the connectivity, security, dependability, and resilience of government communication networks, critical infrastructure, and commercial and security services.

A number of Member States want to spend a portion of their Recovery and Resilience Facility (RRF) funds for space-related initiatives. The space-related budget sought is 2.497 million euros. RRF financing enables Member States to improve their space activities. Some countries, like as France, opt to use the funds for space transportation, while others, such as Italy, use them for a wide range of activities. Greece expressly concentrates its RRF investment on space-based secure connection, with precise objectives for its implementation. Spain is likewise considering using it mostly for connection [11–14].

This new financing gives a chance for smaller member nations, such as Greece and Poland, to develop their space capabilities. In particular, Greece has developed a unique proposal to use a national small satellite project with technical backing from ESA [15]. The Greek National Microsatellite Project is detailed in the Digital Transformation Strategy 2020-2025 [16].

This project is a crucial step toward the realization of Greece's policy for the use of space technology and applications, as well as their integration into the national economy. It involves the creation of a microsatellite group that will cater application for telecommunications and observation of the earth for their use in governmental satellite services, cartography, shipping, agricultural precision topography, and urban planning aiming at the development of innovative integrated programs' services [14,16].

The microsatellite project will make use of ESA's Fibre in the Sky - ESA HyDRON programs, which aim to provide comprehensive secure telecommunications services. In addition, the microsatellite project will assist applications and services for search and rescue, border control, national security, and civic protection. The development of the microsatellite system (space and ground) is projected to improve the capabilities of Greece's high-tech sector. The initiative aims to improve the availability, security, and authentication of government communication networks. In addition, it will deliver high-speed internet in isolated places.

Furthermore, the framework for microsatellite development is expected to be included in the EU GovSatCom, EuroQCI, and Secure Connectivity initiatives announced by the European Union

on July 15, 2020, as well as the 23 February Action Plan for Synergies between civil, defence, and space industries [17,18]. If other nations contribute to RRF financing, a COPERNICUS-style model may be envisaged for the implementation of the space-based secure connectivity effort.

In 2011, NASA claimed that over 100 firms have employed spin-off technology. This application resulted in more than 12,000 lives saved, over 9200 jobs generated, and savings of more than \$6.2 billion [51]. In 2011, infrared satellite photos were used to find nearly 3000 ancient Egyptian villages, and they may potentially be used to safeguard archaeological sites from thieves. In July 2011, a biotechnology firm sent 30 mice on NASA's last shuttle trip to test an antibody that might help prevent bone deterioration, which happens at a faster rate in live organisms in space. Lessons from this study may lead to more effective bone therapies for the world's population.

The U.S. Space economy grew by 12% in 2011, reaching an estimated total of \$289.77 billion. The potential for Space technologies to be transferred and generate innovative processes has been evident since NASA's founding and is forecasted in the future. NASA created an Office of Technical Information and Educational Programs in 1960 to promote transfer programs and support firms in their technology demands. Other countries and Space agencies have also begun to take interest in Space product transfer processes. Scholars and scientists have reported and analyzed this phenomenon in major international journals over the last 50 years, but no one has collected and interpreted this body of publications. This article aims to systematically review Space technology transfer literature and provide direction for future research.

The systematic review of literature focused on the transfer of Space technologies from the Space industry to Earth's industrial system. The search phase was conducted using a rigorous and transparent methodology, constructing a database of 40 articles. The review was limited to studies that focused on the transfer of Space technologies, excluding transfer processes within the Space sector or at an international level. The review was limited to academic literature,

excluding non-peer-reviewed articles and popular articles that did not contribute to scientific theory growth. The literature was selected from 1995-2012, as electronic databases containing the full text of articles have only been available since 1995, and researchers have begun discussing the issue of Space technology transfer in recent years.

The database was analyzed based on key areas of interest in technological transfer processes, including actors, geographical context, industrial sectors, motivations, space technologies, paths, models, impact/effectiveness, and determinants. The results summarize findings from each area and provide definitions of technology transfer. The paper also highlights gaps in the literature and invites further research. The methodology used for identifying and selecting papers is described, followed by a review of the papers based on descriptive characteristics, definitions of technology transfer, and six classification items. The paper also highlights remaining issues for further investigation.

According to Kokkinakos et al. [26], cutting-edge technologies such as social software, data analytics, and so on revolutionize the day-to-day operations of modern organizations at every level and in every way. As a result, it is expected that Digital Transformation has recently become one of the most popular terms on the World Wide Web; because of its importance, many authors have attempted to define and discuss the exact concept of Digital Transformation. This argument emphasizes the need of identifying Digital Transformation, as there is no systematic categorization in academic literature and the borders are frequently blurred. The difficulty of defining the Digital Transformation idea may be addressed after the definitions have been reduced to their fundamental components.

Author(s)	Definition(s)
Fitzgerald et al. McDonald and Rowell-Jones	Use of emerging digital technologies, such as social media, mobile, analytics, or embedded devices, can allow significant business benefits such as improving customer experience, optimizing processes, or developing new business models. As a result, the Digital Transformation extends beyond just digitizing resources and generates value and money from digital assets.
Solis et al.	The realignment of, or fresh investments in, business and technological structures to better engage consumers online at all stages of the customer experience journey.
Collin et al. Gimpel and Röglinger Kane et al.	While digitization is typically defined as the conversion of analog to digital information, the phrases Digital Transformation and Digitalization are used interchangeably to refer to a broader notion involving politics, economics, and social concerns.
Martin	Digital Transformation is now frequently defined as the use of information and communication technology to develop fundamentally new capabilities in business, public governance, and people's and society's lives, rather than just automating tasks.
Westerman et al	Digital transformation is described as the use of technology to significantly increase company performance or reach.
Stolterman and Fors	Digital transformation refers to the changes that digital technology produces or impacts in all areas of human existence.

The many definitions for Digital Transformation (DT) may be grouped in three key elements:

1. Technological - DT is based on the use of new digital technologies such as social media, mobile, analytics, or embedded devices;
2. Organizational - DT necessitates the modification of organizational processes or the development of new business models; and

3. Social - DT is a phenomenon that affects all aspects of human life, such as improving customer experience. Almost all of these aspects are included in the researchers' concept of digital transformation. As a result, we describe Digital Transformation as the application of new digital technologies to achieve significant company benefits while also influencing all areas of consumers' lives.

Digital Transformation has always had a close relationship to industry, and it is presently undergoing massive changes as Industry 4.0 marks the next fourth industrial revolution. It focuses on the complete digitalization of all physical assets and their integration into digital ecosystems with value chain partners. Another key problem is incorporating "digital" into the DNA of business models. This is vital for any company's success and is increasingly becoming a management concern. As with any IT-enabled transformation, simply bringing IT into the business is insufficient; Digital Transformation success is dependent on improvements in process and operations management. To achieve such management, individuals must be taught in a change process that takes into consideration the specific issues posed by IT.

A digital revolution is favorably transforming digital and standardized working settings. Some workplaces are becoming virtualized or remotely controlled, necessitating new communication skills and understanding of virtual worlds. Socially, customers are developing new competencies in order to connect with digital enterprises and survive in the Digital Era. The digital Era appears to be influencing changes in the public sector in addition to fueling enterprise-level innovation. One of the most intriguing issues is governmental digitization, which has the potential to expand in the future. There is also increased interest in the healthcare industry, as there has been major study into the digitization of healthcare in recent years.

Although we recognize the existence of maturity models in this subject, which have mostly been produced by practitioners (e.g., the IDC maturity model), the academic community has yet to adopt a consensus maturity model for Digital Transformation that can be applied to all sectors of activity. As a result, we recommend doing extensive study on the differentiation of connected phrases related to Digital Transformation, as well as developing a maturity model to assess the organizational degree of Digital Transformation.

Conclusion

The current study's goal is to systematically identify scientific and academic publications published in the last ten years on the topic of technology transfer from the space sector to the industrial system. The necessity for systematic examination and analysis of the literature appears to be suitable, as no literature review on the issue of space technology transfer has been conducted to yet. Although Digital Transformation is popular among practitioners, it is often overlooked in the scientific literature, therefore we decided to undertake a literature study. The aforementioned reasoning is well supported by a search in the ISI database using the terms "Digital Transformation" and "Digitalization". On the other hand, enthusiasts may claim that Digital Transformation has fresh components that warrant study and represent exciting research problems.

ABOUT AUTHORS

Shaikh Farisa Tarannum is working with UDICT Mahatma Gandhi Mission University, Aurangabad as Assistant Professor. Her area of interests includes AI, Neural Networking, Natural Language Processing etc.

Aditi Jadhav is working with UDICT Mahatma Gandhi Mission University, Aurangabad as Assistant Professor. Her area of interests includes AI, Natural Language Processing, Deep Learning, Machine Learning etc.

Deepika Dubey is working with UDICT Mahatma Gandhi Mission University, Aurangabad as Assistant Professor. Her area of interests includes AI, Crypto Currency, Natural Language Processing etc.

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